

Impacts of teachers' Training on secondary school students' Learning ...

Impacts of teachers' Training on secondary school students' Learning Attitude and performance

Fayyaz Ahmed

Mphil scholar Institute of Education and Research (IER), University of Baluchistan Quetta.

Dr. Abdul Nasir Kiazai

Director Institute of Education and Research (IER), University of Baluchistan Quetta.

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Abstract

The study was carried out in order to examine the impacts of Teachers' Training on secondary school students' learning attitude and performance. The study was carried out in the secondary schools of district Loralai. It was hypothesized that Teachers' training enhances students' cognitive and physical abilities and encourages the students for the adoption of deep achievements. Students who learn from trained teachers show different and better attitude and performance in academic and social activities than those who do not learn from trained teachers. The sample of this study comprised of the students of secondary schools of district Loralai. A questionnaire regarding the impacts of trained and untrained teachers on the learning attitude and performance of the students was done. Two hundred students were taken as sample from thirty five schools of the twelve union councils of tehsil Bori and one hundred students were taken as sample from twelve schools of the five union councils of tehsil Makhter of district Loralai. It was concluded that trained teachers had much better impacts on students than those of untrained teachers both in rural and urban areas.

Keywords: impacts of teachers' training, difference between trained and untrained teachers, learning achievements

Introduction

Training is an action of teaching a person a particular skill to perform his roles efficiently and effectively. Training is a vital part of development. Most employees have some weaknesses in their organizational skills [Muralidharan & Sundaraman, 2010; Navarro, Zervas, Gesa & Sampson 2016]. Like employees in any organization teachers also need training in order to polish and enhance their teaching skills. [Noah & Olusola 2015; Schroeder & Adesope 2015] Training not only polishes teachers' performance it also helps students learning outcomes. Deficiency among students learning behavior and outcomes, subsequently leads towards the shortcomings in overall organizational performance. Chen-Chung, Kuan-Hsien, Leon Yufeng 2016].

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It is clear that the role of a good and effective teacher is to help his/her students in the process of learning. An effective and good teacher is the one who maintains friendly and nonthreatening environment in the classroom and he/she uses different teaching methods and teaching strategies to keep students more motivated and makes the process of learning interesting and effective. Few examples are group work and classroom discussions. A good and effective teaching is more than just the successful transference of knowledge and skills or application around a particular topic. An Effective teaching process ensures that, this surface approach to learning is replaced by deeper, student driven approaches to learning that analyze, develop, create and demonstrate understanding. Teachers have been known to have important influence on students' academic achievement and they also play an important and crucial role in educational achievements, because the teacher is ultimately responsible for translating educational policies and principles into actions; based on practice during interaction with the students. An excellent teacher is the one who quite frequently makes it possible for the learners to learn well. Many research studies have been carried out about both the conditions that affect learning, the teacher's personal characteristics or classroom activities, show that there is a little agreement among the researches on the field of education about the qualities of an effective teacher.

In Balochistan 2 main public teacher training institutes, which are B.O.C and Extension Center and other is Provincial Institute for Teacher Education. The number one center was created in the period of 1976 for the object and works on National Curriculum to provide feedback to central administration. Their character and activity was carried out by a group of skillful in various disciplines. Responsible for uplift of elementary and secondary teachers in the positions of P.C.T and C.T, respectively, through pre-service teachers who are only above the hand of supervision of extension center. (aggarwal, 2010)The main purpose of this new subject and courses were to overcome the matter teachers commonly tackle during teaching process. The new subjects were important but fixed on the subject areas only. it was maximum about of 15 days. Choosing teachers who are employees for training programs was often undertaken to education institutions like school directors or sometimes headmaster teachers, thus result in regain repetitions of teachers, and many teachers cannot get the opportunity but could not find it. (P.D, 2008) after in the period on 1996, Institute of provincial for Teacher Education programmed created by assistance of Asian Development Bank which means the creating best education policy. And they can create good education training center for teachers both male and females.

Research Methodology

Qualitative and Quantitative research methodology is used for this study. For this purpose teachers and students in the public schools of Loralai District are taken for the collection of data. For the data collection random sampling technique has been used. With the help of Survey data has been collected. For this purpose questionnaires have been given to teachers and students. Data analysis has done by using descriptive and correlative techniques. Thus the field work also created some questions like, what is the impact of the teacher's training for the secondary school students in Baluchistan generally in the district of Loralai. Last and finding questions consist or include a set of MCQS through the response. Information of standard or qualitative included in the questions explained in results.

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Objectives of the Study

This study has the following objectives.

- To study the impacts of teacher training on students' learning attitude.
- To study the relation of students' learning attitude and their performance.
- To study the difference between trained and untrained teachers' teaching styles and students' outcomes and responses.
- To analyze the effectiveness of training programs on the attitudes of the teachers towards teaching profession.

Specific Objectives

- To study teacher's training impact on students' attitudes and behaviors.
To study specific teaching practices'

Hypothesis

Teachers' training enhances students' cognitive and physical abilities and encourages the students for the adoption of deep achievements. Students who learn from trained teachers show different and better attitude and performance in academic and social activities than those who do not learn from trained teachers.

Limitation of the Study

The population of the study is limited to District Loralai of Baluchistan. The population is limited to secondary schools' children. In the study researcher will explain, benefits of the teacher training for the secondary school students in the Loralai District. He will explain that the teacher training is the best process for every school to obtain the required results and for molding and polishing the behavior of the students. Because when the trained teachers and hard working teachers teach the student than the students learning attitude is positive. We know that education is the tool which molds the behaviors of the individuals. Education is a changing agent. The secondary level students are usually the students of the age of adolescence. Such students should be handled with great care and this duty can only be performed by the trained teacher. The trained teacher guides the students in right direction. Only through the advance level of teachers' training the huge change in students' learning attitude could be overcome. In far flung district like Loralai a trained teacher plays the role of back bone in the character building and personality building of the students. Only a well trained teacher could understand the psyche of the students well and could guide the students about their destination.

Tools of research:

In this research following tools were used.

Questionnaire:

Data was collected by through a structured questionnaire. This questionnaire included 38 items. There were five choices for the students to give their answers. It was told to the students that all the data given by them will be used just for research study. All the information provided by them would be kept in secret. After this they were agreed to provide all information.

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Observations:

This is very helpful method to know how much a trained teacher affects the students, their learning and attitude, about the personality of students as well as the psychology of learners. In the sampling schools we went for a week to observe the target groups. In these schools we observed following factors:

- personality of the learners
- Student's behavior with fellows.
- Student dressing
- Student school timing
- Learners interest in studies.
- Students' strength the in class.
- Students hand writing style.
- Absent ratio of students from schools.

Population of study:

This research study was conducted in district Loralai. There are two Tehsils of this district which are given below:

- Thesil Bori
- Thesil Makhter

Schools of both the tehsils are included in the population.

Data collection Procedure

The questionnaire was designed as a survey paper. The data was collected from each class teacher of class 7, 8, 9 and 10. Permission was taken from the relevant school's principal for this survey data collection. Questionnaires were used to collect relevant information and data from the students in very short time. The reason I took my data from questionnaires is that it is less time taking. One source of data was used in this to get reliable data results to support my research in the Particular School. To know student's achievements and trained teachers teaching respondents were asked to indicate total of 38 items and the response utilized were

- 1: strongly disagree
- 2: disagree
- 3: neutral
- 4: agree
- 5: strongly agree.

Variable of the study

This research is about the impacts of teachers' training on the secondary school students' learning attitude and performance and teachers' training and its effects on student's achievements. In this study we have done random sampling and collected data to know about effective teachers teaching and their effect on student's academic achievements and change in behavior.

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Finding and Results

Results of Data analysis are shown in the following tables.

Tehsil Bori (No. of union councils 12)

Table 1: Data from students about trained teachers.

Total number of students 100

1:Communication My teacher...						
S.No.	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD
1	Maintains fair and firm discipline without being too strict.	50	20	10	15	05
2	Is flexible in accommodating for individual student needs.	46	28	14	08	04
3	Listens and understand student's point-of-view.	53	20	08	12	07
4	Explains concepts clearly.	49	30	10	06	05
5	Always help us set goals for our learning and track our progress.	50	35	06	03	06
6	Voice easily reaches back benchers.	55	36	03	02	04
2: Management My Teacher						
7	Maintains enough classroom discipline so the class and I can learn	70	20	02	03	05
8	Provides relaxed atmosphere in classroom.	45	38	12	03	02
9	Display strict attitude towards class control.	10	14	15	35	26
10	Present Test and Assignment marks within a reasonable time frame.	60	35	01	04	00
11	Engages students by asking questions related to topics	75	15	03	05	02
12	Manages classroom time and pace well	75	20	00	03	02
13	Makes positive contributions in lessons/discussions.	56	37	00	04	03
3: Instructions/Curriculum My Teacher						
15	Gives and writes clear instructions.	70	20	00	07	03
16	The teacher explains the contents in an easy and understandable method	70	20	03	05	02
17	Gives homework and checks it properly and highlights my mistakes	80	10	00	05	05
18	Grading system is fair and reasonable and all students are satisfied.	60	25	08	05	02
19	Uses methods of evaluation(quiz, assignment, exam, etc) that reflect important aspect of subject matter and provide fair evaluation of students learning	70	15	00	10	05

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20	Provide clear directions and explaining on assignments and tests.	60	30	05	04	01
21	Maintains clear rules for behavior in classroom and takes responsibility for promoting good behavior both in classroom and around school	53	30	00	11	06
4: Teaching Styles and Strategies My Teacher						
22	Gives background knowledge.	80	17	00	03	00
23	Encourages participation in discussions/questions	70	15	05	06	04
24	Presents subject materials in interesting way.	60	25	05	07	03
25	Involves me in making choices and decision about my school activities.	50	30	10	06	04
26	Maintains close link between what is actually taught and with previous knowledge of students.	80	15	04	01	00
27	Use different styles to explain things.	85	13	00	00	02
28	Explains clearly and gives deeper understanding of concepts.	50	20	09	12	09
29	Gives assignment and homework relevant to subject matter.	45	35	10	07	03
30	Regularly provides my class with clear goals.	48	30	10	10	02
5: Feedback and motivation My Teacher						
31	Supports and motivates us to work hard.	70	20	00	05	05
32	Offers encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as constructive criticism.	67	23	04	04	02
33	Show interest and is enthusiastic about teaching this class.	60	25	10	05	00
31	Supports and motivates us to work hard.	66	30	00	04	00
32	Offers encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as constructive criticism.	65	20	08	05	02
33	Show interest and is enthusiastic about teaching this class.	70	15	05	07	03
31	Supports and motivates us in curricular and co curricular activities.	68	20	10	02	00
32	Offers encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as constructive criticism.	69	14	07	06	04
33	Show interest and is enthusiastic about teaching the subject matter.	70	15	05	08	02
34	Provides with useful feedback on my work.	75	17	03	05	00
35	Gives relevant homework.	68	22	00	05	05

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36	Respond with good feedback on homework and projects so that we can improve.	67	20	05	05	03
37	Teaches students to plan, observe, and evaluate their teaching activities.	70	20	03	08	02

Table 1.1: Data from students about untrained teachers.**Total number of students 100****Tehsil Bori (schools of twelve union councils area included)****1:Communication My teacher ...**

S.No.	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD
1	Maintains fair and firm discipline without being too strict.	20	20	05	50	05
2	Is flexible in accommodating for individual student needs.	23	30	03	40	04
3	Listens and understand student's point-of-view.	26	25	04	42	03
4	Explains concepts clearly.	35	19	08	33	05
5	Always help us set goals for our learning and track our progress.	27	19	04	32	18
6	Voice easily reaches back benchers.	29	21	03	37	10

2: Management**My Teacher**

7	Maintains enough classroom discipline so the class and I can learn	24	20	02	39	15
8	Provides relaxed atmosphere in classroom.	27	25	07	36	05
9	Display strict attitude towards class control.	25	19	10	34	12
10	Present Test and Assignment marks within a reasonable time frame.	22	19	07	30	22
11	Engages students by asking questions related to topics	30	25	05	30	10
12	Manages classroom time and pace well	23	20	00	40	17
13	Makes positive contributions in lessons/discussions.	21	21	08	40	10

3: Instructions/Curriculum**My Teacher**

15	Gives and writes clear instructions.	27	23	00	44	06
16	The teacher explains the contents in an easy and understandable method	21	22	07	45	05
17	Gives homework and checks it properly and highlights my mistakes	26	20	04	47	03
18	Grading system is fair and reasonable and all students are satisfied.	21	19	03	50	07

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19	Uses methods of evaluation(quiz, assignment, exam, etc) that reflect important aspect of subject matter and provide fair evaluation of students learning	23	17	05	45	10
20	Provide clear directions and explaining on assignments and tests.	28	20	04	44	04
21	Maintains clear rules for behavior in classroom and takes responsibility for promoting good behavior both in classroom and around school	23	17	06	46	08
4: Teaching Styles and Strategies My Teacher						
22	Gives background knowledge.	21	19	10	43	07
23	Encourages participation in discussions/questions	23	17	05	50	05
24	Presents subject materials in interesting way.	22	19	08	44	07
25	Involves me in making choices and decision about my school activities.	20	20	70	50	03
26	Maintains close link between what is actually taught and with previous knowledge of students.	25	20	05	43	07
27	Use different styles to explain things.	26	21	06	40	07
28	Explains clearly and gives deeper understanding of concepts.	23	17	10	45	05
29	Gives assignment and homework relevant to subject matter.	22	22	09	40	07
30	Regularly provides my class with clear goals.	21	19	08	47	05
5: Feedback and motivation My Teacher						
31	Supports and motivates us to work hard.	29	21	05	42	03
32	Offers encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as constructive criticism.	22	24	02	47	05
33	Show interest and is enthusiastic about teaching this class.	23	23	04	45	05
31	Supports and motivates us to work hard.	21	21	06	44	08
32	Offers encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as constructive criticism.	24	20	07	45	04
33	Show interest and is enthusiastic about teaching this class.	20	19	06	43	12
31	Supports and motivates us in curricular and co curricular activities.	27	21	03	44	06
32	Offers encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as constructive criticism.	24	19	07	42	08
33	Show interest and is enthusiastic about teaching the subject matter.	23	20	05	47	05

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34	Provides with useful feedback on my work.	22	22	05	46	05
35	Gives relevant homework.	21	19	03	50	07
36	Respond with good feedback on homework and projects so that we can improve.	24	21	02	47	06
37	Teaches students to plan, observe, and evaluate their teaching activities.	26	20	05	43	06

Discussion:

The purpose of my research is to investigate and know the impacts of teacher's training on the students' learning attitude and performance. I have also tried to know the change in behavior of the students of secondary schools in district Loralai , when they are taught by the trained teachers. The results proved that trained teachers' have positive impacts on students' achievement. The results of this study are consistent with the results of Moon, Mayes & Hutchinson (2004) who stated that trained teachers can use their ability to impact and influence pupils to perform. Moreover, trained teachers know different teaching methods. Our findings show how training of the teachers affects the students' learning. How a trained teacher works in accordance to the psychology of the secondary school students and achieves his goal by changing the behavior of the students.

Conclusions:

It is concluded from the findings that teacher training has strong impacts on the academic achievement of the students. Pedagogical skills are improved with the help of training program. The process of teaching and learning could be made easy and interesting if both the teachers and learners take interest, because it is observed that a trained teacher has not only command on the subject , but also he is able to use more and more methods and techniques which he has learnt in training , in his teaching. A trained teacher also uses audio and video aids to teach his/her students. Such methods are interesting for the students.

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